

SPATIAL SUPPORT FOR ENVIRONMENTAL MONITORING OF LAND USE: DEFINITION AND APPLICATION TOOLS**Mamonov K.**<http://orcid.org/0000-0002-0797-2609>**Goi V.**<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1822-4478>**Frolov V.**<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8045-3963>*O.M. Beketov National University of Urban Economy in Kharkiv, Ukraine*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17878297>**Abstract**

It has been established that issues remain unresolved regarding ensuring the growth of land use efficiency through the application of monitoring systems, geoinformation tools, and the formation of spatial support, determining the impact of environmental and land use factors.

The aim of the study is to develop tools for creating spatial support for environmental monitoring of land use. The following tasks were solved within the framework of the study: substantiation of theoretical provisions for determining spatial support for environmental monitoring of land use; proposal of a definition of spatial support for environmental monitoring of land use; characterisation of tools for the formation of spatial support for environmental monitoring of land use.

A definition of spatial support for environmental monitoring of land use is proposed as a system for the formation and use of information support and control over the application of information on the environmental status of land use in the urban environment using modern technological means and geoinformation systems, taking into account the characteristics and directions of interaction with various groups of stakeholders (stakeholders), including state and local institutions, aimed at increasing the efficiency of land use and environmental safety.

Tools are proposed for the development of monitoring of land use of nature reserve fund objects in regions based on the results of the formation of information about the state and spatial, regulatory, legal and instrumental support for monitoring, diagnostic and analytical system of factors and the application of methods for the integrated assessment of the level of land use of nature reserve fund objects, mathematical modelling and neural networks, which made it possible to develop geoinformation monitoring maps for making informed decisions on increasing the level of use of nature reserve fund objects. The developed tools create opportunities for permanent diagnosis and control of the level of land use of nature reserve fund objects in the regions and determine the directions for the formation and implementation of monitoring on information and analytical support.

Keywords: *spatial provision, environmental monitoring, land use, geodetic provision, tools.*

Relevance of the study. The transformation processes taking place in the field of land use are related to the consequences of Russian aggression, the negative impact of external factors and internal imbalances, the reform of the land relations management system at the regional level, the growing importance of environmental factors, require changes and a rethinking of approaches to the development and application of spatial support for environmental monitoring (EM) of land use (LU).

The implementation of processes for the formation of a modern system of self-government is determined by the need to apply geographic information systems (GIS) to ensure land use. A regulatory and legal framework has been created in this area, but issues related to the application of GIS in the land relations system, the training and use of specialists at the local level in accordance with modern conditions, and the availability and accessibility of geographic information systems and technologies have not been sufficiently addressed.

At the theoretical and methodological level, a quantitative basis for making informed decisions on the formation of spatial support (SS) for environmental monitoring of land use in urban areas has not been developed based on the development and implementation

of an assessment method and the application of mathematical modelling of factors of spatial support for environmental monitoring of land use.

Considering the above, an urgent task is to resolve a complex set of issues related to ensuring the effective use of land, taking into account the directions and characteristics of spatial support and the impact of environmental factors based on the implementation of monitoring procedures.

Issues remain unresolved regarding ensuring the growth of environmental monitoring effectiveness through the use of monitoring systems, geoinformation tools, and the formation of spatial support, determining the impact of environmental and land use factors.

Review of literary sources. Existing scientific studies lack a unified approach to substantiating spatial monitoring of land use in urban environments. Even at an insufficient level, environmental monitoring of land use in urban environments has been defined. In particular, a systematic approach has been implemented in the study [1], where environmental monitoring is considered as a comprehensive scientific and information system for observing, assessing and forecasting the state of the environment and living organisms under the influence of anthropogenic factors.

The functional approach is characterised by a set of interrelated actions for the formation and implementation of environmental monitoring:

- observation;
- information gathering;
- assessment of the actual state of the object of observation;
- forecasting of the future state and its assessment;
- management and regulation of environmental quality [2]. In this regard, the management aspects of environmental monitoring implementation are of particular importance [2].

In the context of the formation and use of environmental monitoring, factor and institutional approaches are implemented for land use. Taking into account international experience and areas of application of geographic information systems, the following developments are highlighted [3, 4].

According to the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine «On Approval of the Regulations on Land Monitoring», land monitoring is defined as a system for observing the state of land with the aim of timely detection of changes, their assessment, prevention and elimination of the consequences of negative processes. The object of monitoring is all land, regardless of the form of ownership. Soil monitoring is an integral part of land monitoring.

The following types of land monitoring have been identified:

- national – on all land within the territory of Ukraine;
- regional – in areas characterised by uniform physical, geographical, ecological and economic conditions;
- local – on individual land plots and in individual parts (elementary structures) of landscape-ecological complexes [5].

The following functional features of land monitoring have been identified:

- processes related to changes in soil fertility (development of water and wind erosion, loss of humus, deterioration of soil structure, waterlogging and salinisation), overgrowth of agricultural land, contamination of land with pesticides, heavy metals, radionuclides and other toxic substances;
- the condition of the coastlines of rivers, seas, lakes, bays, reservoirs, estuaries, and hydraulic structures;
- processes related to the formation of gullies, landslides, mudflows, earthquakes, karst, cryogenic and other phenomena;
- the condition of land in populated areas, territories occupied by oil and gas production facilities, treatment plants, manure storage facilities, fuel and lubricant storage facilities, fertiliser storage facilities, motor vehicle parking areas, toxic industrial waste and radioactive material disposal sites, and other industrial facilities [5].

The objectives of monitoring are: to introduce a system for the exchange of information on land relations between information interaction entities; to improve the quality of services in the field of land relations; to improve the quality of land resource

management at the state, regional and local levels; to increase the investment attractiveness of land resources and improve the business climate in the field of land relations; to create an information base for the modernisation of land relations.

Monitoring is based on the following principles: timeliness and comprehensiveness of information received and stored in the monitoring system; objectivity of information; promptness of provision and entry of information into the monitoring system; openness of monitoring results.

The directions and features of land use monitoring, taking into account environmental aspects, are presented in works [6–10].

It is proposed to define spatial support for environmental monitoring of land use as a system for the formation and use of information support and control over the application of information on the environmental status of land use in the urban environment using modern technological means and geoinformation systems, taking into account the features and directions of interaction with various groups of stakeholders (stakeholders), including state and local institutions, aimed at increasing the efficiency of land use and environmental safety.

Main part. In the system of spatial provision of environmental monitoring, tools for creating a quantitative basis are applied using the appropriate method. The development of a method for the integrated assessment of the level of formation and use of land in nature reserve fund objects in regions includes a set of interrelated stages:

- construction of a diagnostic and analytical system of factors for monitoring the use of land in nature reserve fund objects in regions;
- identification of local factors of the level of formation and use of land of nature reserve fund objects at the regional level;
- characterisation of systemic factors of the level of formation and use of land of nature reserve fund objects;
- building models to determine the systemic factors of the level of formation and use of natural reserve fund objects in regions;
- building a model of an integral indicator of the level of formation and use of natural reserve fund objects;
- assessing weight coefficients using the hierarchy analysis method;
- determining the integral indicator;
- interpreting the results obtained.

Local factors influencing the formation and use of land in nature reserve fund objects at the regional level are determined using expert and analytical methods. The characteristics of systemic factors of the level of formation and use of lands of nature reserve fund objects are carried out in accordance with the generalisation of existing theoretical and methodological provisions and the developed diagnostic and analytical system. They are formed by local factors in the system of monitoring the use of lands of nature reserve fund objects in regions.

Systemic factors affecting the formation and use of nature reserve fund objects in regions are determined

on the basis of mathematical models constructed using the geometric mean, taking into account the values of local factors:

systemic factor of the level of regulatory and legal support affecting the formation and use of land in nature reserve fund objects in territories (EL_1):

$$EL_1 = \sqrt[19]{\frac{EL_{11} * EL_{12} * EL_{13} * EL_{14} * EL_{15} * EL_{16} * EL_{17} * EL_{18} * EL_{19} * EL_{110} * EL_{111} * EL_{112} * EL_{113} * EL_{114} * EL_{115} * EL_{116} * EL_{117} * EL_{118} * EL_{119}}{EL_{118} * EL_{119}}} \quad (1)$$

systemic factor in the development of information and analytical support for the formation and implementation of land monitoring of nature reserve fund objects in regions (EL_2):

$$EL_2 = \sqrt[15]{\frac{EL_{21} * EL_{22} * EL_{23} * EL_{24} * EL_{25} * EL_{26} * EL_{27} * EL_{28} * EL_{29} * EL_{210} * EL_{211} * EL_{212} * EL_{213} * EL_{214} * EL_{215}}{EL_{210} * EL_{211} * EL_{212} * EL_{213} * EL_{214} * EL_{215}}} \quad (2)$$

systemic factor of the level of rational use and protection of natural resources identified factors influencing the development of monitoring the formation of lands of natural reserve fund objects in regions (EL_3):

$$EL_3 = \sqrt[11]{\frac{EL_{31} * EL_{32} * EL_{33} * EL_{34} * EL_{35} * EL_{36} * EL_{37} * EL_{38} * EL_{39} * EL_{310} * EL_{311}}{EL_{310} * EL_{311}}} \quad (3)$$

systemic factor of instrumental support for monitoring the formation of lands of nature reserve fund objects in regions (EL_4):

$$EL_4 = \sqrt[4]{EL_{41} * EL_{42} * EL_{43} * EL_{44}} \quad (4)$$

systemic factors threatening the formation of land areas designated as nature reserves in the regions (EL_5):

$$EL_5 = \sqrt[14]{\frac{EL_{51} * EL_{52} * EL_{53} * EL_{54} * EL_{55} * EL_{56} * EL_{57} * EL_{58} * EL_{59} * EL_{510} * EL_{511} * EL_{512} * EL_{513} * EL_{514}}{EL_{510} * EL_{511} * EL_{512} * EL_{513} * EL_{514}}} \quad (5)$$

systemic factors of the natural value of land in nature reserve areas in the regions (EL_6):

$$EL_6 = \sqrt[7]{EL_{61} * EL_{62} * EL_{63} * EL_{64} * EL_{65} * EL_{66} * EL_{67}} \quad (6)$$

systemic factors of socio-economic value of territories (EL_7):

$$EL_7 = \sqrt[9]{EL_{71} * EL_{72} * EL_{73} * EL_{74} * EL_{75} * EL_{76} * EL_{77} * EL_{78} * EL_{79}} \quad (7)$$

systemic factor of effective management of land formation and use of nature reserve fund objects at the regional level (EL_8):

$$EL_8 = \sqrt[15]{\frac{EL_{81} * EL_{82} * EL_{83} * EL_{84} * EL_{85} * EL_{86} * EL_{87} * EL_{88} * EL_{89} * EL_{810} * EL_{811} * EL_{812} * EL_{813} * EL_{814} * EL_{815}}{EL_{810} * EL_{811} * EL_{812} * EL_{813} * EL_{814} * EL_{815}}} \quad (8)$$

A model has been developed for an integrated indicator of the level of formation and use of land in nature reserve areas in the regions:

$$I_{EL} = k_{EL_1} * EL_1 + k_{EL_2} * EL_2 + k_{EL_3} * EL_3 + k_{EL_4} * EL_4 + k_{EL_5} * EL_5 + k_{EL_6} * EL_6 + k_{EL_7} * EL_7 + k_{EL_8} * EL_8, \quad (9)$$

The weight coefficients are assessed using the hierarchy analysis method.

fund objects in the regions are presented on the radar (Fig. 1).

The results of the assessment of the integral indicator of the formation and use of nature reserve

Figure 1. Results of the assessment of the integral indicator of the formation and use of nature reserve fund objects in the regions, relative units.

The obtained values of the integral factor of land use of nature reserve fund objects range from 2 to 3 on

the integral factor scale, which indicates an insignificant level of land use of nature reserve fund

objects in the regions, as well as the neglect of issues related to the formation and use of these territories, the unsystematic creation of information and analytical support, and the lack of monitoring of nature reserve fund lands at the regional level. It should be noted that regulatory and legal support for monitoring the use of land in nature reserve fund objects has been developed, but its application is characterised by a low level of implementation at the regional level. There is a certain imbalance in the directions of land use in the ecological network and in the interaction of state, regional and local institutions regarding their formation and use. Therefore, there is a need to develop scientific and methodological recommendations for the formation

and use of information and analytical support for monitoring the use of land in nature reserve fund objects in the regions.

In order to develop a system for monitoring the level of land use of nature reserve fund objects and presenting data by region, it is proposed to carry out a geoinformation analysis of the land use of nature reserve fund objects by constructing a corresponding geoinformation map of the values of the integral factor of the level of land use of nature reserve fund objects by region, a geoinformation monitoring map. The scheme for constructing a geoinformation map is presented in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Diagram of the structure of a geoinformation map of the integral factor of land use by nature reserve fund objects by region

The proposed scheme for implementing geoinformation analysis of the land use level of nature reserve fund objects involves presenting the results of the integral factor by region. To implement it, the input data of the integral factors of the land use level of nature reserve fund objects is loaded into the ArcGis environment. After that, cartographic spatial information is generated in the form of an shp file. Upon completion of these stages, links are established between the geodatabase of integral factors of land use of nature reserve fund objects and cartographic data of Ukraine's regions. Based on the established links, an analysis of the integrated factors of land use

in nature reserve fund objects by region is performed. After the analysis, the results of the analysis are obtained and a scale of the impact of factors of land use in nature reserve fund objects by region is formed. At the final stage, a geoinformation map of the integral factor of land use of nature reserve fund objects by region is formed.

As a result of the study, a scheme for the formation and implementation of information and analytical support for monitoring the use of land of nature reserve fund objects in regions has been developed (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Scheme of formation and implementation of information and analytical support for monitoring the use of land of nature reserve fund objects in regions

Conclusions. A set of tools for developing land use monitoring of nature reserve fund objects in regions is proposed based on the results of information formation on the state and spatial, regulatory, legal and instrumental support for monitoring, diagnostic and analytical system of factors and the application of methods for the integrated assessment of the level of land use of nature reserve fund objects, mathematical modelling, and neural networks, which made it possible to develop geoinformation monitoring maps for making informed decisions on increasing the level of use of nature reserve fund objects. The developed tools create opportunities for permanent diagnosis and control of

the level of land use of nature reserve fund objects in the regions and determine the directions for the formation and implementation of monitoring on information and analytical support. It should be noted that spatial data is used to build the monitoring system, where geodetic support is of great importance.

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